

***Paenibacillus xanthanilyticus* sp. nov., a xanthan-degrading bacterium isolated from soil**

Simin Ashraf,¹ [Mohammad Reza Soudi](#),^{1,*} Mohammad Ali Amoozegar,² Mahdi Moshtaghi Nikou³ and Cathrin Spröer⁴

¹Department of Microbiology, Faculty of Biological Sciences, Alzahra University, Tehran, Iran;

²Department of Microbiology, Extremophiles Laboratory, Faculty of Biology and Center of Excellence in Phylogeny of Living Organisms, College of Science, University of Tehran, Tehran, Iran;

³Microorganisms Bank, Iranian Biological Resource Centre (IBRC), ACECR, Tehran, Iran;

⁴Leibniz Institute DSMZ – German Collection of Microorganisms and Cell Cultures, Inhoffenstraße 7B, 38124 Braunschweig, Germany.

*Correspondence: Mohammad Reza Soudi, msoudi@alzahra.ac.ir or soudimr@gmail.com

Abstract

A xanthan-degrading bacterium, strain AS7^T, was isolated from soil and its taxonomic position was determined using a polyphasic approach. Strain AS7^T was a Gram-stain-variable, spore-forming, motile, aerobic, rod-shaped bacterium. Phylogenetic analysis based on 16S rRNA gene sequence analysis revealed that strain AS7^T belongs to the genus *Paenibacillus*, sharing the highest level of sequence similarity with *Paenibacillus phyllosphaerae* PALXIL04^T (98.0 %). The cell-wall peptidoglycan contained meso-diaminopimelic acid. MK-7 was the dominant isoprenoid quinone and the major fatty acid was anteiso-C₁₅ : 0. Polar lipids consisted of diphosphatidylglycerol, phosphatidylglycerol, phosphatidylethanolamine and two unknown phospholipids. These chemotaxonomic characteristics were consistent with the isolate belonging to the genus *Paenibacillus*. The G+C content of the genomic DNA was 51.0 mol% and the DNA–DNA hybridization value between strain AS7^T and *P. phyllosphaerae* PALXIL04^T was only 14.4±2.5 %. On the basis of phylogenetic analyses, phenotypic and chemotaxonomic characteristics, and DNA–DNA relatedness value, strain AS7^T represents a novel species of the genus *Paenibacillus*, for which the name *Paenibacillus xanthanilyticus* sp. nov. is proposed. The type strain is AS7^T (=IBRC M 10987^T =LMG 29451^T).

Keywords: *Paenibacillus*; polyphasic taxonomy; xanthanolytic bacterium.